

Importance of Mental Health in Work Place

Abhinav.B*, Dr.BhuvanaRamachandran**

*Research Scholar, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

OrcidID:0000-0002-7808-2953; Email: abhinavbalakandyjhk@gmail.com

**Research Professor, School of Social Science and Humanities, Srinivas University,
Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

OrcidID: 0000-0001-8103-1789; Email: bhuvanaram90@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

Purpose: *Globalization has been providing various employment opportunities; commercial businesses have progressed with the help of the fast pacing technologies. The workers are the backbone of an enterprise as it is only through them a product enters the market and meets the customers. They should be given good working conditions and satisfactory benefits to sustain their livelihood. A good workplace helps a person to develop in all aspects of his/ her life. A company's productivity and the reputation can go in harmony when the workers are given small leaves for maternity as well as for paternities, providing a weekly session arranged for focusing on the stress relieving of the workers, their incentives; overall a concern to their mental health and well- being. A stressed job and an inappropriate workplace will affect the worker mentally. He/ she are expected to behave in a ruthless manner affecting even their family.*

Objective: *This paper intends to shed light upon the importance of mental health in the work place among a small number of people.*

Methodology/Approach: *Data can be collected by preparing a questionnaire of 10-15 questions using the googleform focusing upon the conditions of the workplace. A face to face interaction with the people who are mentally affected by the bad working conditions should be made. Further queries to be undertaken upon the measures taken to improve the workplace. A psychological approach should be made to finally check on how a better working condition affects the mental health of the worker.*

Findings/Result: *If the methods are employed in a finite fashion, findings will reflect upon how far the numbers of people arementally affected by their work, the sacrifices they are undergoing to sustain their livelihood in spite of the bad environment. It also will reflect the effect upon their normal life, and the importance of mental health in the work place.*

Keywords: Globalisation, fast pacing, paternities, googleform, fashion

1. INTRODUCTION:

Mental health problems have become the worst disability problem nowadays. The commercial business progress at a rapid speed with the advent of technology. The joint efforts of the workers are solely responsible for the outcome.

“Work, which can be defined as mental or physical activity that has productive results, is organized into jobs” An individual working in an enterprise or anywhere will be able to provide a maximum satisfactory output from his/her profession only when their mental health is stable and anchored. It is the mental health which determines and governs a person's actions and exertions. Any company can remain in the market only when it is able to exercise its abilities much more ahead of its competitors. The workers are the only way they can do so. Hence, it is the responsibility of an entrepreneur to safeguard their worker's privileges and mental well-being.

The environment in the work place must be employment friendly. Such employment friendly workplace can have an adverse effect upon the enterprise. With a great job satisfaction the entrepreneur can augment the productivity, they will be able to satisfy the customers and with that the overall profitability of the firm will increase. The workers must be given a sense of individual value. They must be safeguarded. The entrepreneur can offer benefits like Employment State Insurance Corporation (ESIC), discount benefits, etc. to its employees. To ensure the mental stability in the employees, the entrepreneur can offer certain wellness programs like providing free Yoga classes, free membership in the gyms or provide any discounts in body development programs and health

programs. In this way the employees will feel satisfied with the behaviour of the company and they will feel very concerned about their workplace.

An employee always wish to be noticed and get appreciated for the work he/she provides to the firm. They might have given heart and soul for it. Hence among a group they naturally feel to be discerned. The entrepreneur can utilise this opportunity by remembering the names and the other details of the workers. Doing so, he/she will have a sense of belongingness and will not feel like a hierodule of the company.

An entrepreneur not only can decorate his/her own office but also can improve the working atmosphere and the conditions of the workers. As it is from there, the worker has to build up his/her career and to move their livelihood. Cleanliness is very important. A clean working place with adequate fresh room and the refreshments can be set up. The entrepreneur can instruct his/ her workers to give particular emphasis on the cleanliness also. The entrepreneur can encourage or can pass statements of appreciation to worker who keeps the environment clean and tidy.

A business firm surely has to undergo various strategies of misunderstanding and also some other problems associated with it. The entrepreneurs have to find time to get redressed about his/ her workers grieving. The entrepreneur must carefully listen to the problems by the workers and must find a firm and sound solution, keeping in mind not only the problem not to arise later but also not to low down the dignity of the other employee, if any such occasion arises. By doing so, the employees will feel that they are the top priority for the firm. Various firms can establish a women's cell or women grievance body in their company to document their issues. The entrepreneur in the firm can try to establish gender equality in respect of the economic benefits also.

The time schedule and the work timings must be favourable to the employees. There must be fairness in the working hours of the office timings. The employee towards the end of the day should not be worn out. Remember, the same employee should turn back to work the next day also, so it is very important to check any monotonous activities do not arise. The entrepreneur can show the importance of the timings by making him/her itself punctual to the enterprise. He/ she can set an example to the employees. The entrepreneur must also ensure that including him/her should report in the workplace at one fixed time. If such uniformity is practised by the superiors, then the subordinates will follow. There must also be flexible working hours in the enterprise. The employees should have recess or break appropriately so that they could spend some time with their colleagues and relax themselves. This helps them to boost up their mentality and get prepared.

Family is an important element for all. There will be lady staffs that may have to send their baby to the various day cares in the city. An entrepreneur can try to provide day care in their firm itself. A particular space can be allotted for such, at the same time it must be somewhere quite far from the actual working area. So that, the conduct of their business do not get disturbed. Such good deeds by the entrepreneurs show not only the polite nature of the management but also it will encourage the workers to re-join to their workplace after their maternity leave.

Parenting is an essential factor. Motherhood is very important. It must also be remembered that the fatherhood is as important as that of motherhood. A considerable paternity and maternity leaves can be given to the employees. Such acts can also be encouraged in the enterprise as once when the employees feel that their life is also given a priority in the firm, they will feel dedicated towards their job.

'All work no play makes Jack a dull boy'-it is true that an employee who is not given a timely leisure will consequently result in low productivity. The hectic work which they endure must not be continued. The entrepreneur must also ensure to provide some leisurely activity for the employees. It will boost the employees and will give them a relief from their timely works. Such leisurely moments are necessary in an enterprise because in the present scenario the recovery for the well-being of any employee is very important. The entrepreneur should realise that it helps an employee to restore the mental energy. Restoring the mental energy is very important for an employee in any field of work as it helps them to sustain a state of positivity. It helps them to get motivated. Only then they will be able to cope up with the fast pacing technological world, increase the productivity and able to meet the client's demands. If not, these challenges will be emotionally overloaded. An employee must be mentally disengaged from the particular type of work during the off-job time. This relaxation will help them to reduce the work tensions and help to regain the mental and physical energies. It will in turn help them to master new skills required for the job. The company can try to conduct some cultural activities or other programs and make the employees involved in it. Such creative activities will be highly beneficial to the employees with stress full jobs. This helps in building up a good communication among the managers and the staffs as it is this platform which will help them in breaking the impairment among them. They try to develop a sense a unity in them. A healthy employee is a boon and a great asset for an enterprise. Being physically and mentally fit is very important for a business. Too much of sitting in front of the computer system will result in weakened and high strained muscles. Providing some physical fitness activities will help to loosen their ligaments. For the growth of the company it is very essential for the Manager to develop and maintain happy employees and also a satisfied environment.

A minimum leave must be provided to the employees. Leaves like privilege leaves, sick leave, maternity leave, casual leave, marriage leave. Privilege leaves must be given to the employees as it will help them to loosen up their mental thoughts. Other than that, a vacation with their family will help them maintain a relaxed mentality. The employers can also provide casual leaves to the workers as sometimes certain unforeseen personal requirements should be fulfilled. The employer should not force the employees regarding matters concerning their personal demands.

A child's birth is a remarkable stage in a woman's life. Unfortunately, in a certain societal norms, the woman after child birth is forced to quit jobs and is to stay behind and look after the child. Workers must be given maternity leaves for at least 20-26 weeks. The employers are required to notify the women staffs in the firm in writing about the maternity leave that avails to them. Providing such benefits will not incur any additional cost or expense to the employers. The women who apply for maternity will likely to be aged between 25-35, this comprises middle aged level workforce. If the employers try to retain them then they do not have to bear any cost for hunting for new recruitment or in replacing them. This not only helps the firm to maintain a strong workforce but also helps to maintain gender equality. Addition to this, the employer can also take steps to encourage women to engage in work from home after their delivery. The employer and the women must be aware that no termination can ever be possible on a woman who has gone for maternity leave not unless or until a valid reason is produced due to unwanted activities from her side. When a company tries to break the old tradition of marginalising the women from enjoying the economic benefits and trying to break the norms of preserving a woman's life in the four walled corners of a room, the company in turn is likely to benefit and enjoy a major increase in its reputation by encouraging women empowerment.

The company can also provide paternity leave. It is from home where its benefits actually commence. The fathers who really love their families take leave and help their partners from home. This helps in building a stronger relationship of trustworthiness and care. Every woman during post-birth really aspires for the father to be around to help her do the household works and to take care of the baby.

Diverse behaviour is another element where many managers or the superior staffs are still unprepared to deal with. They might be knowledgeable, still not quite ready enough to deal with multiplicity factors. This might lead to generation of unhealthy working atmosphere. In order to avoid such bad implications, the Manager must be ready to grasp various ways to overcome it. This can only be done with the help of communication. Communication must be openly created among the workers irrespective of the caste, race, creed, sex, professional rank, etc. only then the Manager will be able to understand the vast diverse groups in the organisation and will be able to develop a personal value with the workers. A communication is said to be effective only when the communicator gets the appropriate feedback for what has been communicated. So the Managers can try to encourage the diverse group of people to provide casual informal feedbacks. Another way is to develop empathy. *"Empathy is an important way to deal with more subtle problems because it helps the manager understand the diverse employee's point of view"* (Luthans 40). Considering the workers point of view or walking in other's shoe is a good way to build a strong relationship with the employees. Various kinds of problems may arise in an organisation. In order to provide suitable solution to all the problems, the best method that a Manager can adopt is to talk from other's point of view and try to avoid any situations which give rise to further complications.

Job stresses are the stresses which really affect the life of an individual. The Managers must see to it that when an employee enters the workplace, he/she must feel very comfortable and not get tensed about any workloads. The Managers can try to provide non-crowded work areas. It is very difficult for certain people to put their entire focus upon a work when there is a huge crowd. These crowded areas may create a large amount of noise and may cause a big disturbance for the employees making it difficult to work. Certain work, in order to yield an accurate output may require a high level of concentration. The working atmosphere is also as important because it can trigger the mental wellbeing of the employees. Working in a hot or warm atmosphere with crowded and noisy colleagues will surely lead to a rise in the blood pressure level or any other mental problems and disorders of the employees. Increasing the stress level of the workloads will prove to be harmful. The working atmosphere must be free from any kind of pollutions.

Downsizing in any form is harmful for the enterprise and for the Manager. The employees must not feel unsafe in the working environment. At the same time the Manager must also see to it that the workers are not degraded or devalued for the effort they put to the enterprise. There will be lot of competitions in the market. A business is always about competitions. The more risk a Manager takes the more profit he/she can bag it up. But it is to be made clear that no competition pressures should be imposed upon the workers. The Manager must understand and be firmly clear that, the more tension is heated up upon the workers the more stress they will have to endure. This will affect the quality and the quantity of the output which in turn leads to a down fall in the productivity. So it is better not to exercise any pressure upon the workers. So in order to tackle the competition pressure, the Managers must try to smoothly handle the workers. Make them comfortable by talking openly to them or the Managers must

give a stress-free classes or activities to the workers during the time of competition. Towards the end, they must feel to work for the enterprise during this crucial time with all their efforts.

Extra benefits should be awarded to those who provide extra sacrifice to the enterprises. It is always a good sign from the part of the Manager to plan award or benefits economically or in any other way to his/her workers. Providing such is always an appreciation for the workers and they will develop a tendency to work for the enterprise. The workers must not get exhausted from the various shifts of their work. There are workers who prefer shifts during day time and some may prefer shifts during the night. The Manager must try to find out or chalk down those people who prefer to work at any point of time they feel comfortable with. Some workers might be family people; they would like to work only during the day time and some might like to spend late night in the office. There should be a circular rotation in the workers regarding the shifts. At the same time, the Managers must also check whether there are any workers who prefer to work during any time, if so, such realisations at the right time will help the Manager in many ways as such workers will happen to be a greatest asset to the enterprise.

In order to maintain efficiency in the work process, it is better the Managers try to keep up a respectful behaviour, self-discipline among each other. But the Managers must also see to it that the rules imposed in the organisations do not turn into bureaucratic. Some workers may not feel like to work under strict rules, some might feel like an unwanted authoritative upon them. Whereas there will be some workers who do not wish to obey the rules and guidelines set by the company or the Managers. Such situations are quite normal cases in the eyes of a business firm. Hence the Managers must see to it that there should be strict rules which are able to keep up to the company's policies, able to maintain the trade secrets, etc. and also these rules must act as a guidelines to the workers and not take the role of some force which controls them and make them look like puppets. The workers must not feel that they are actually stringed and are being operated by the Managers or any other supervisors. Bureaucratic rules always exploit the relationship between the workers and the Managers.

Trading is not same as it was during the earlier periods. The modes of trade have changed, the process of trade have also changed. With the development in globalisation, there has been a good development in technology also. The utilisation of the advanced technologies will help the business in many ways. Such kind of technology helps the firm to increase its productivity, output, etc. The advanced technology also has various good benefits for the workers. With the advanced technology, the workers will be able to work without facing any high stress or may not get tired. As mentioned earlier, certain work force may require great efforts to produce an output in good quality and quantity. In order to do so, in normal cases, the workers will be assigned to work at late hours (may be with extra pay or may not be), it normally tires the workers making them to possess a bad impression upon his/her boss. In the worst case it might affect their family conditions also. On the other hand, the Managers can adopt advanced technological methods which can double the output; the workers in turn will not feel overburdened with works. This not only tries to remove heavy burdens from the shoulders of the workers but also at the same time it acts to reduce any additional expenses. With the help of the advanced technologies, the Managers do not have to bear the burden of extra pay to the tired workers making them to engage in extra labour. Also the workers can get accessed to new technologies prevalent in the market which in turn will help in raising their standard. There will be a good influence in the mentality of the workers as well because the workers will have the feeling that they are working with advanced technologies.

“Harmony is more important than productivity” (Luthans 363). A peaceful environment is one where any individual really wishes to rely upon. America is always termed as a capitalist nation. As far as the Americans are considered, they are more focused on the results. The workers with poor workforce are always chucked outside. “Human behaviour in organisations is complex and often difficult to understand” (Nelson, Quick 2). The human mentality actually transforms and gets focused into the workforce. The great productivity can be let out only when the workers are given the freedom to work as per his/her comfort by not breaking the rules and regulations of the company. The Manager must see to it no additional pressure is loaded upon the workers shoulders. As there may be cases where the workers may tend to lose their normal mentality which will affect the goodwill of the company.

REFERENCE

1. Luthans, Fred. *Organizational Behaviour*, The McGraw-Hill Companies, New York, 2011.
2. <https://robertrestoblog.wordpress.com/2017/04/05/chapter-14-jobs-and-the-design-of-work/>
3. <https://www.cengage.co.in/>.